

HYDROUSA project solutions towards water scarcity mitigation and organic micropollutants evaluation for safe water reuse

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Abstract: Global warming is a well-known problem worldwide, nonetheless its consequences are not fully clear yet. One of the main related issues is the increasing water scarcity around the world. With this purpose, the European H2020 project HYDROUSA aims at evaluating innovative, regenerative, and circular solutions for nature-based water management of Mediterranean coastal areas, closing water loops; nutrient management, boosting the agricultural profile; based on circular value chains in three Greek islands (Tinos, Lesvos, and Mykonos) and theoretically replicate HYDROUSA solutions in 25 sites around the world. ICRA task inside this project is the evaluation of each of the water sources. Selected micropollutants: pharmaceuticals (including antibiotics), endocrine-disrupting compounds, pesticides, personal care products and compounds included in the EU Watch List 2018/840 are being monitored in each of the considered routes of fresh water obtention in the HYDROUSA project.

Keywords: Water Reuse; Nature-Based Solutions; Micropollutants Monitoring.

Climate change is one of the main problems for society, its consequences are springing among the world and provide an uncertain future. According to World Health Organization, by 2025, half of the world's population will be living in water-stressed areas. This matter is especially important in places affected by tourism, for example the Mediterranean countries. Thus, searching solutions to this treat has become one of the priorities of these regions. HYDROUSA project (*Demonstration of water loops with innovative regenerative business models for the Mediterranean region*) tests several kinds of technologies to obtain water for unconventional sources (Figure 1). HYDROUSA solutions include wastewater treatment and reuse through upflow anaerobic sludge blanket digestion (UASB) (including biogas production and energy recovery in the wetlands system); nature-based solutions for seawater through a mangrove system to obtain freshwater and rainwater harvesting. The role of ICRA is the evaluation of the best treatment-train as a function of contaminants removal. In addition, fate of organic micropollutants will be studied in terms of the transfer from the water phase to plants (uptake) irrigated by regenerated water.

Fig 1: HYDROUSA aims at closing the loops to obtain new sources of freshwater/alternative water sources.

Organic micropollutants compounds, if not completely removed by the conventional wastewater treatment plants, are discharged into the environment as different studies have already demonstrated^{1,2,3}. Even if some of them can be found at low

concentrations, they may have an impact in the ecosystems. This is the case of, for example, antibiotics and the related concern for the spread of antibiotic resistance genes.

The list of organic micropollutants was generated based on the prioritization based on data about occurrence, removal in wastewater treatment, ecotoxicity, and bioaccumulation. The final list of emerging pollutants that are being monitored at ICRA includes pharmaceuticals (including antibiotics), pesticides, endocrine-disrupting compounds, personal care products and compounds included in the EU Watch List 2018/840. Samples of wastewater, river water, seawater, and rainwater from the Greek demonstration sites, all of them used as sources for water reuse, were collected and analysed. Samples were preconcentrated using HLB solid-phase extraction cartridges and injected in a UHPLC Acquity Ultra Performance™ Waters Corporation (Milford, MA, U.S.A.) coupled to a 5500 QTRAP mass detector (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA).

Differences among the different water sources have been highlighted and the information is being applied for a sound evaluation of the technologies and focus on the most present and/or relevant compound (Figure 2). A second monitoring campaign will be launch in 2021 to evaluate the performance of the technologies as well as the difference among years and seasons. A third sampling campaign will also be carried out including the analysis of local crops irrigated with reclaimed water. Thus, specific methods of extraction are being updated to analyse if/which micropollutants are up taken by those crops and vegetables.

Fig 2: Presence of 3 selected classes of micropollutants in three water matrices (Greek islands sampling campaign)

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